

A Machine Learning Methodology for Network Anomalies Detection in O-RAN Networks

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Abstract—Despite the extensive research and various existing systems for detecting and classifying anomalies in operational networks, Internet Service Providers (ISPs) continue to seek efficient methods to handle the increasing number of network traffic anomalies they encounter in their daily operations. This research paper tackles the challenge of automatically detecting network traffic anomalies using Machine Learning (ML) techniques. We introduce a straightforward classification approach based on Deep Neural Networks and assess its accuracy, precision, and recall performance. To evaluate the proposed neural network, we train and test it using data collected from a real LTE deployment of 10 base stations.

Index Terms—Anomaly detection, O-RAN, Non-realtime RIC, Machine learning, rApp

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for mobile data services and the diversity of connected devices and applications has led to the need for more flexible, scalable, and autonomous networks. The Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) has emerged as a promising solution that offers flexibility, interoperability, and cost-effectiveness in the deployment and operation of cellular networks. In O-RAN, disaggregation and virtualization of network functions enable the utilization of vendor-neutral hardware and software components from various suppliers, fostering a more open and competitive ecosystem. Furthermore, by utilizing the so-called RAN intelligent controllers, O-RAN provides a more intelligent and autonomous approach to network management via machine learning solutions based on the data generated by constant network monitoring [1].

As the complexity and heterogeneity of networks grow, ensuring their reliable and efficient operation becomes

paramount. Anomaly detection plays a crucial role in identifying and addressing irregularities or deviations from normal behavior in the network operation. An anomaly in the network can arise from various sources, such as configuration issues, equipment failures, security breaches, or performance degradations. Detecting and mitigating these anomalies in time is essential to maintain network performance, ensure service availability, and enhance security [2]. Traditional anomaly detection techniques, such as statistical and clustering algorithms, have been widely applied in various domains. However, adapting these techniques to the unique characteristics of O-RAN networks poses significant challenges. O-RAN networks exhibit dynamic behavior, different traffic patterns, and frequent changes in network configuration due to the virtualized nature of their components [3]. Therefore, more advanced and adaptive methods are required to detect anomalies in O-RAN networks effectively.

Machine learning (ML)-based approaches have gained considerable attention in anomaly detection due to their ability to learn from historical data and identify complex patterns [3]. ML algorithms, such as Isolation Forest [4], One-Class Support Vector Machines (SVM) [5], and LSTM-based models [6], offer potential solutions for detecting anomalies in software-defined cellular networks. By leveraging data from various sources, such as performance metrics, logs, and alarms, ML-based methods can provide real-time insights into network behavior and enable proactive anomaly detection.

This paper proposes an ML-based anomaly detection algorithm compatible with the O-RAN standard. The algorithm is designed to be implemented as a rApp on top of the O-RAN's

reconfiguration instructions via the A1 interface to the near-RT RIC that controls the base station where the anomaly occurred.

Fig. 2. Anomaly detection rApp scheme

We used Jupyter Notebooks, Python 3.7.2, Keras, and TensorFlow to develop a prototype of the proposed solution. The performance evaluation of the prototype was conducted in a typical scenario involving network monitoring. The data used for building the prototype was sourced from [17]. The dataset is collected from a live LTE deployment and consists of two weeks of data from a group of 10 base stations recorded at 15-minute intervals. The dataset is presented as a CSV file, where each row represents a sample obtained from a specific cell at a particular time. Even if the obtained data is from a traditional LTE architecture, the same parameters can be recorded and received via the E2 and O1 interfaces. Each sample contains the following features:

- **Time**: the timestamp (in hh: mm format) showing when the sample was recorded
- **CellName**: a string used as a unique identifier of the cell from which the sample was recorded. The format of this identifier is xLTE, where x is the base station identifier, and a is the cell within the base station.
- **PRBUsageUL** and **PRBUsageDL**: represent the level of resource utilization in a specific cell, expressed as a percentage of the Physical Radio Blocks (PRBs) that were in use for the past 15 minutes, separately measured for uplink(UL) and downlink(DL).
- **meanThr_DL** and **meanThr_UL**: indicates the average carried traffic in megabits per second (Mbps) for the past 15 minutes, separately measured for uplink(UL) and downlink(DL).
- **maxThr_DL** and **maxThr_UL**: represent the maximum carried traffic in Mbps observed in the last 15 minutes, separately measured for uplink (UL) and downlink (DL).
- **meanUE_DL** and **meanUE_UL**: indicate the average number of user equipment (UE) devices that were simultaneously active for the past 15 minutes, separately measured for uplink (UL) and downlink (DL).
- **maxUE_DL** and **maxUE_UL**: represent the maximum number of user equipment (UE) devices that were simultaneously active in the last 15 minutes, separately measured for uplink (UL) and downlink (DL).

- **maxUE_UL+DL**: represents the maximum number of user equipment (UE) devices that were active simultaneously for the past 15 minutes, regardless of the uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) differentiation.
- **Unusual**: labels used for supervised learning. A value of 0 indicates that the sample corresponds to regular operation, while a value of 1 identifies unusual behavior.

Figure 3 depicts our proposed ML solution for the rApp. The final neural network architecture was selected after basic hypertuning, with which the optimal number of neurons in the hidden layers, dropout rate, learning rate, epochs, batch size, and recall/ precision threshold were selected based on results such as accuracy and precision/recall ratio. The final model's architecture consists of the following:

- **Input layer**: The input layer is the foundational component of the neural network, responsible for accepting and processing the raw data or features that serve as the input to the model. As input for our neural network, we have used all of the dataset features mentioned above, excluding "Time", "Cellname", and "maxUE UL+DL".
- **Hidden layers**: The hidden layers are the intermediate layers in the neural network that play a crucial role in feature extraction and representation learning. Our model comprises three hidden layers. These layers consist of 8, 6, and 4 neurons, each equipped with the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function, used to facilitate the network's ability to capture complex patterns within the dataset. ReLU is computationally efficient and helps mitigate the vanishing gradient problem, making it a popular choice in deep learning.
- **Dropout layers**: Overfitting of the model is a common problem in deep neural networks, so to prevent it, after each hidden layer, we have incorporated dropout layers. The dropout layers serve to randomly deactivate a fraction of neurons during training, effectively regularizing the network and improving its generalization to unseen data.
- **Output layer**: The output layer is the final layer of the neural network, responsible for producing the model's predictions or outputs based on the processed information from the preceding layers. Given the problem's binary classification nature, our output layer consists of a single neuron with a sigmoid activation function. The sigmoid activation function is well-suited for binary classification tasks like our use case. It transforms the raw output of the network into a probability score, indicating the likelihood of an input belonging to the positive class. Values close to 0 suggest a low probability of belonging to the positive class, while values close to 1 indicate a high probability.

V. EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED MODEL

Before training the model, the dataset was divided into three parts: 70% of the dataset was used for training the model, 10% for cross-validation during the training, and 20% was used for testing the model. The number of training epochs is 100, with a batch size of 32 and a learning rate of 0.01. Figure 4

Fig. 3. Model of neural network

depicts the model loss graph of our neural network. The loss graph plots the training and validation loss value throughout training epochs. We analyzed the graph to assess our machine learning model's training progress and performance. The major observations after the analysis are:

- **The training loss** steadily decreases with each epoch, indicating that the model effectively learns from the training data. This trend suggests that the model is more accurate in predicting the target variable as the training progresses.
- **The validation loss** initially follows a similar decrease pattern as the training loss. We see deviations in the validation loss compared to the training loss pattern. However, those deviations are around 1%, so they will not significantly affect the model and can be ignored for now.

Fig. 4. Model loss graph

After evaluating the algorithm's performance, we obtained the following results:

- **Accuracy:** The overall accuracy of our model is 0.7571, indicating that 75.71% of the traffic is classified correctly. This accuracy level suggests that the algorithm can effectively classify the network traffic, but there are some false positive/negative predictions.

- **Precision:** The precision is 54,43%, indicating that a large amount of usual traffic is classified as unusual (false positive results).
- **Recall:** The recall score is 0.7563, meaning that 75.63% of abnormal traffic is classified correctly.
- **F1 score:** The F1 score, which combines precision and recall, is 0.6630. This score provides a balanced measure of the algorithm's performance, considering false positives and negatives. A high F1 score indicates an excellent overall trade-off between precision and recall. Although scores below 0.7 are generally considered unfavorable, the confusion matrix depicted in Figure 5 reveals a well-balanced trade-off between false positive and false negative outcomes.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix

For both classes, we have found around 24% false predictions. Usually, when machine learning is used for anomaly detection, it is permissible to have more false positive results, which can be manually checked. However, since the algorithm is intended for network automation, it is better to keep the false positive and false negative results similar. Because too many false positives would result in clogging the network with reconfiguration messages, but too many false negative messages will decrease the network's performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has proposed an ML-based anomaly detection algorithm for the O-RAN standard, implemented as a rApp on O-RAN's non-real-time controller. The algorithm effectively learns from the training data, leading to accurate predictions as indicated by the decreasing training loss. The validation loss follows a similar pattern, with minor deviations. While there are some false positive/negative predictions, the algorithm demonstrates the ability to classify network traffic satisfactorily. The precision and recall scores highlight the algorithm's performance in correctly identifying abnormal traffic. The achieved F1 score indicates a balanced trade-off between false positive and false negative predictions.

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